

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Suhara P Muhammadkutty

Research Scholar ,

Gandhi Shikshan Bhavan's

Research Guide: Dr. Frances Vaidya

Abstract

Teacher is the most vital single factor of influence in the system of education. It is the teacher who matters most as far as the quality of education is concerned. The educational process is governed by the extent of receptivity and initiative. The well-equipped teacher is supreme in education. At all times the teacher is the pivot in the system of education. This is especially the case in a period of basic change' and reorientation. The study aimed at finding the difference between emotional intelligence and Teacher Effectiveness. of secondary school teachers on the bases of gender and types school board. And the data was descriptively and inferentially analysed. Emotional intelligence scale was constructed by Dr. Ekta Sharma and. used for the purpose of the study with the necessary permission. Teacher Effectiveness scale was constructed by the researcher. 600 secondary school teachers were selected from different SSC and CBSE schools of Raigad district. Descriptive analysis and Anova i.e. . 't' test done for analysis. . The descriptive analysis revealed that for the mean score of Emotional Intelligence and Teacher Effectiveness, the male Secondary school teachers are marginally higher than the female Secondary school teachers. Similarly the SSC teachers are marginally higher than the CBSE school teachers when we compare the mean score. In the inferential analysis, the 't' test revealed that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence on the bases of gender and types of school board.. For Teacher effectiveness the t test revealed that there is no significant difference on the bases of gender. However there is a significant difference in the Teacher Effectiveness of secondary school teacher on the

bases of types of school board. The SSC school teachers are moderately higher than the CBSE secondary school teachers.

Key words: Emotional intelligence, Teacher Effectiveness, Education, Teacher, Gender, Type of School Boards, Secondary school teaches

1. Introduction

Education cannot be delimited to a particular age, stage or span of life, but it is a continuous process and encompasses all the inspiration and stimuli which act upon an individual during his transit from cradle to the grave. At every moment, the interaction with the environment gives him a new experience, a new teaching, it will not be wrong to say that life is education and education is life. The teacher is the most significant feature in the learning environment provided by the institution.

1.1 Emotional Intelligence

Teaching is about much more than just usually passing information. An effective teacher has a strong belief in his/her capability to exercise control over his/her emotions, behavior and thinking i.e., in total he/she should be emotionally intelligent. An Emotionally Intelligent teacher will be a better guide.. He must have knowledge along with a set of skills that Emotional Intelligence provides, such as- emotional awareness, self-assessment, self- control, optimism, stress tolerance, self- regard, flexibility, social skills and so on.

1.2 Teacher Effectiveness

Teacher effectiveness plays an important role in teaching –learning process. An effective teacher does not create image of the students rather help the students to create the image of their own by understanding the problems of the students and helping them, by making any subject interesting, by controlling the class and by being fair with the students while dealing with them. Teacher effectiveness is an area of research which is concerned with relationship between the characteristics of teachers, teaching acts and their effects on education and discriminating between more or less effective teachers.

1.3 Review Of Related Literature

In the present research, the investigator has scanned and reported most of the relevant studies done in India and abroad in the field of Emotional Intelligence and Teacher Effectiveness of the Secondary school teachers.

1.4 Aim Of The Study

The study aimed at finding the difference between Emotional Intelligence and teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers on the bases of Gender and types school board.

1.5 Objectives Of The Study

- To study the difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely Female and Male Secondary School Teachers.
- To study the difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.
- To study the difference in the Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely Female and Male Secondary School Teachers.
- To study the difference in the Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.

1.6 Hypothesis Of The Study

- There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely Female and Male Secondary School Teachers.
- There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.
- There is no significant difference in the Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely Female and Male Secondary School Teachers.
- There is no significant difference in the Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.

1.7 Delimitation Of The Study

- The study was conducted in SSC board and CBSE board schools of Raigad only.
- The study was delimited to 600 secondary school teachers..

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Methodology Of The Study

The study aimed at finding the difference between Emotional Intelligence and Teacher Effectiveness of secondary school teachers on the bases of gender and types school board. The data was descriptively and inferentially analyzed. Anova i.e. 't' test done for analysis.

2.2 Techniques Of Sampling

In the present study, a two stage sampling procedure is used where at the first stage the schools were selected and at the second stage teachers were selected. In the first stage of sampling, the researcher initially collected the list of the schools. For the purpose of the study the researcher selected the schools on the basis of their types namely SSC and CBSE.

2.3 Tool Used

- The researcher used a readymade tool for Emotional Intelligence constructed by Prasad Corporation (New Delhi) that is ready made tool.
- Teacher Effectiveness tool constructed by researcher for the purpose of the study.

2.4 Procedure

After administering the tools on the sample, the scoring was done as per the scoring system.

2.5 Descriptive Analysis

Data collected for the main study was analysis by descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. To find out the difference between variables Anova i.e. 't' test done for analysis.

3. Result

3.1 Descriptive Analysis For Emotional Intelligence

Group	Sample size	Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
Female	310	155.01	158	162	6.423	0.390	1.732
Male	290	155.51	157	162	6.859	0.870	-0.753
SSC Board	224	155.61	158	162	5.967	1.045	-1.590
CBSE Board	376	155.43	158	162	6.458	0.584	-0.260

Interpretation: The mean score of Emotional Intelligence the male Secondary school teachers are marginally higher than the female Secondary school teachers. Similarly the SSC teachers are marginally higher than the CBSE school teachers when we compare the mean score.

3.2 Descriptive Analysis For Teacher Effectiveness

Group	Sample size	Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
Female	310	177.17	177	179	12.644	4.894	2.157
Male	290	178.67	176	178	17.112	11.217	1.860
SSC Board	224	178.45	178.5	179	14.603	8.042	2.627
CBSE Board	376	178.02	175	172	15.270	9.018	2.502

Interpretation: The mean value of Teacher Effectiveness indicates that the male Secondary school teachers are marginally higher than the female Secondary school teachers. Similarly the mean value of Teacher effectiveness of SSC Secondary school teachers are slightly higher than the CBSE secondary school teachers when we compare the mean score.

3.3 Inferential Analysis

- **For Hypothesis 1** There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely male and female secondary school teachers.

Table 1

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	<u>l.o.s</u>	Result
Female	310	156.05	6.610	1.957	0.05	Accepted
Male	290	155.01	6.423			

Interpretation of 't'

The t value of female, male teachers is 1.957 which is greater than the tabulated value at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of female and male teachers of secondary school teachers.

- **For Hypothesis 2** There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.

Table 2

Board	N	Mean	SD	't' value	<u>l.o.s</u>	Result
CBSE	376	155.51	6.859	0.189	0.05	Accepted
SSC	224	155.61	5.967			

Interpretation of 't'

The t value of SSC and CBSE teachers is 0.189 which is greater than the tabulated value at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of CBSE and SSC teachers of secondary school.

- **For Hypothesis 3** There is no significant difference in the Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely male and female secondary school teachers.

Table 3:

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Lo.s	Result
Female	310	179.92	18.870	2.107	0.05	Rejected
Male	290	177.17	12.644			

Interpretation of 't'

The 't' value of female, male teachers is 2.107 which is greater than the tabulated value at 0.05 level. This implies that there is a significant difference in the Teacher Effectiveness of female and male Secondary School teachers.

- **For Hypothesis 4** There is no significant difference in the Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.

Table 4

Board	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Lo.s	Result
CBSE	376	178.67	17.112	0.167	0.05	Accepted
SSC	224	178.45	14.603			

Interpretation of 't'

The 't' value of SSC and CBSE teachers is 0.169 which is greater than the tabulated value at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in Teacher Effectiveness of CBSE and SSC Secondary School teachers.

4. Conclusion

- There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely Female and Male Secondary School Teachers.
- There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.

- There is a significant difference in the Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely Female and Male Secondary School Teachers.
- There is no significant difference in the Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards

5. Suggestions

The study could also include Municipal schools, ICICI and the IB boards too. The rating scale can also be altered, so that the secondary school students could be the respondent. A comparative study is also recommended between the types of schools and board affiliations.

6. References

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